

FEATURES OF PROGRAMS IN ACCORDANCE WITH THE POSSIBILITIES OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE EDUCATION IN SCHOOL.

Abstract: This article provides an opinion on the correspondence of programs to school educational processes in the organization of foreign language lessons.

Key words: process, technologies, environments of schools, educational institutions, software

One of the most effective ways to improve the process of teaching foreign languages is the use of computer and Internet technologies in the education system. The computer-information model of education is a kind of transitional stage from the system of traditional methods of teaching one's own languages to the system of open education of the modern – foreign information society. The basis for the implementation of information technology by a professional specialist is the process of informatization. We are talking about technologies: the creation of virtual libraries, educational software (electronic libraries, electronic textbooks, dictionaries), the creation of information databases of universities and schools, multimedia programs, virtual discussion clubs, consultation centers, educational information environments of universities and schools, databases, containing catalogs of all educational courses for various types of educational institutions.

The introduction significantly increases the level of information competence of students, in particular, such skills as using the Internet to find the necessary educational information are developed; training is the application of the following computer computer information methods of teaching reference publications; the use of electronic educational use of information

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propaganda personality of a student, capable of adequately acting in a real situation, communicative and socio-cultural orientation. Working with a computer involves mastering a certain system of knowledge, abilities and skills, which are more commonly called computer literacy. There are two types of computer literacy: household and professional. For teachers of foreign languages, professional computer literacy can mean:

- 1) knowledge of the technical and didactic capabilities of computers and training software;
- 2) the ability to develop scripts for educational computer programs¹;
- 3) the ability to correctly set a task for a software engineer;
- 4) the ability to use applied programs (educational and auxiliary).

At the present stage of development in the process of teaching foreign languages, much attention is paid to the development of computer technologies – multimedia hypertexts technologies (teleconferences, teleconferences, technologies, technologies, communication lessons, etc.), technologies for constructing virtual reality. In the process of teaching a foreign language, a computer can perform functions that should ensure the formation of linguistic or communicative competence: 1) carry out training and living in a dialogue mode; 2) simulate real speech animations and videos, create the effect of contact with the language environment; 3) visually presenting the speech situation, use it as a stimulus, support in the process of educational dialogue; 4) provide communication in the target language using computer communication lines, situations using graphics.

YOUNG ACADEMIC

Modern computer tools allow you to create new teaching, training, or controlling. This kind of programs are created in special educational and are widely used in the process of independent and home language educational programs in English are "Tutor", "11 lessons of English", "English Gold", "Reward" (very high quality, but expensive program), "Triple play plus in English", "English on holidays", "Hello ... America! ..." Bridge in English " " Professor Higgins " " English for communication " " Talking Oxford Dictionary " and others. For almost every section of the textbook, you can pick up material from one of the named programs and use its help in the lesson as an aid when introducing new lexical or grammatical material, practicing pronunciation, when teaching dialogic speech, reading and writing, as well as when testing. There is a huge number of discs for any age and degree of "advanced" in language learning: "Lingua Land", "English from A to Z", "English for beginners", etc., for preschoolers , for preparation for universities , as well as for those who want to master English perfectly," English: The path to excellence ". I will dwell in more detail on the following programs: "11 lessons of English" (authors G.D. Skibitsky, I.N. Kuchinava and others, Center of Informatics, Izraelviki), "Tutor" (authors A.Ya. Zhilin, E. E. Pichkin et al, International Center for Financial and Economic Development, Moscow), "English discoveries".

1) The program "11 lessons ..." includes grammatical phenomena studied in the YLVI guides of a comprehensive school: lexis, modal verbs. Each lesson is devoted to a separate topic and includes a large number of exercises that can be used both for training and consolidation, and for monitoring students' knowledge. The first pages contain reference material that the student can use when needed, and the vocabulary used in the exercises. There are many exercises, and the level of difficulty is increasing. The teacher has the opportunity to find a task within his abilities for each student, which is a good incentive in

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work.

2) The "Tutor" program differs from the "11 lessons ..." program in that it can be used both for teaching oral speech and for mastering grammatical material. It will be about using the "Tutor" program to master grammar. The program includes quite a few exercises on different grammatical topics: modal verbs, degrees of comparison of adjectives and adverbs, articles, etc. From these forms of the verb, the student must choose the correct one by pressing the changing mice. If the option chosen by him turned out to be incorrect, then the computer gives him the opportunity to correct the mistake: this means, the student is only using the mouse, so the pace is quite fast. The student receives an assessment immediately after completing the exercise: an "excellent" mark appears on the screen ("quite good," "satisfactory," or "more work to be done"). In case of difficulty, students can use the help of the program. In the section "Analyzing Difficult Passages from the Main Text" there is a grammatical reference book in which you can find all the necessary information: the rule for the formation of a particular grammatical phenomenon and examples of its use in speech. The "Tutor" program can be used in lessons in the 6th-9th grades, and as a computer support in other grades, for example, when repeating grammatical material.

3) "English discoveries" is an interactive multimedia English language learning program.

199 - traditional classes, 299 - classes in the computer class. The program is a series of teacher CDs for learning English, divided into three main levels. The first module of the series is for beginners. It is intended for learners who are completely new to English. Here, the main focus is on the alphabet, numbers and basic everyday vocabulary - food, clothing, etc. Next come - basic information, high and practical - business English. The program covers all four aspects of language proficiency (reading, writing, speaking and hearing) using English and real life situations. The program has introductory and final tests for each module.

The work of students in this program is fully controlled with the help of a special management system "Teachers Management System". She has great potential. The Class list option allows you to enter class lists.

Having found the last name of the student, you can see how many points he performed on a particular test. In the Lessons option, you can create lessons for specific classes and individual students. The study of any topic of the school curriculum begins with a new vocabulary. Having studied a certain set of vocabulary in a traditional lesson, you can continue this work in a computer class. The work is carried out in a certain order: Explain, Training, Game, Test. In the first stage, Explain, student listens, read, and translate words. When finished, go to the "Training" stage, perform exercises for substitution and correct spelling. In the first stage of the training, student listens to the words and find an image of this elephant in a picture on a computer. The computer determines if the answer is correct. In the "Game" stage, students write crosswords and play Tic-Tac-Toe. At the final stage, a control task is performed. Writing skills are improved in the "Writing" section. There, students, using the given templates, write letters, draw up reports, fill out forms. The section "Reading" contains texts of various types (stories, announcements, letters, poems and articles). At the first stage, students listen to the text without visual support, this contributes to the improvement of listening skills. Then the text is displayed on the screen. Students use special functions to translate and listen to the text the required number of times. At this stage, there are also functions for highlighting the main idea and keywords in the text. Each

student works at an individual pace. After the familiarization stage, at the training stage, detailed work with the text takes place. Students fill in the blanks with meaningful words and answer questions. The final stage is the test. If the student fails the test, he goes back to the preparatory stage and then repeats the test. This is very convenient and results in a good quality of knowledge. After listening, reading the dialogue in the "Speaking" section, the students recorded their speech and compared their own pronunciation with the speech of native speakers. Through repeated repetition, the students achieved perfect pronunciation. This form of work is especially popular among our students who want to speak in English well.

THE LIST OF LITERATURE

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